

Implementing a simple, dynamic and controllable AI delineation tool in clinical settings

Nis Sarup¹, Maximilian Lukas Konrad¹, Marie Louise Madsen Lange Sevdal¹, Simon Long Krogh¹, Christian Rønn Hansen^{1,2}, Irene Hazell¹, Ebbe Laugaard Lorenzen¹, Carsten Brink¹

¹Laboratory of Radiation Physics, Department of Oncology, Odense University Hospital, Odense, Denmark

²Department of Clinical Research, University of Southern Denmark, Odense, Denmark

Abstract This paper describes some of the development, decision-making processes, and outcomes of implementing a locally hosted service for automatic segmentation, using in-house trained models complying with national and international guidelines, of medical scans in cancer radiation therapy. By integrating this service, we significantly reduce the time from scanning to treatment planning, as the system automates tasks traditionally performed manually, thereby reducing the need for manual editing. We detail the service's architectural structure, discussing critical decisions in its design and addressing the constraints posed by the hospital's broader IT infrastructure. Our results highlight that automatic segmentation improves workload, and sheds light on practical considerations and challenges of embedding such technological solutions in a clinical setting.

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) in radiotherapy, especially in auto-segmentation, has shown promising advancements in increasing consistency in segmentations compared to manual segmentations^[3]. Yet, the practical application of AI in clinical settings lags behind.

To address this, we developed the AI Inference Service (AIS), a system designed to facilitate the use of AI for clinical auto-segmentation in radiotherapy in our department, using AI models tailored to our needs. AIS focuses on robustness, ease of use, and adaptability to various clinical scenarios.

The AIS operates transparently for the end-user, see Figure 1. In a typical workflow, scanners send images directly to the treatment planning system. With AIS, scanners transmit images simultaneously to the treatment planning system and AIS.

Figure 1: The workflow of the AIS as seen by the end-user.

Modular Service Structure

AIS is composed of four main modules, see Figure 2, each serving a distinct function within the service:

- Gateway: As an extension to a DICOM database, it filters incoming images, determining their suitability

for segmentation and the appropriate AI model for processing.

- Watchdog: This module monitors a directory for new image sets, triggering AI inference processes. It ensures timely execution of AI scripts and limits the system to only have as many active inference processes as the available computational resources allow.
- Inference: Manages the conversion from DICOM to Nifti format, runs the nnU-Net^[1] for segmentation, post processing, and converts the output back to a DICOM RTStruct file.
- Return service: Tracks both successful and unsuccessful inferences, managing the output RTStructs accordingly. It returns completed segmentations or error-coded RTStructs for failed processes. Currently, both the DICOM protocol and standard file copying are supported.

Figure 2: Modular structure of AIS.

Each delineation of an image set is allocated a unique directory on the inference machine, where all files relevant to that image set are stored. The system renames this directory based on the process stage, facilitating easy tracking and logging. In the event of successful segmentation and delivery, the directory is deleted. Otherwise, it is preserved with logs to aid in error identification and resolution.

2 Materials and Methods

System Architecture and Technical Specifications

The AIS is engineered to integrate into the existing IT infrastructure of our radiotherapy department. Image sets are sent directly to the normal recipient systems, while simultaneously being sent to AIS. The system's software components are primarily written in Python and Matlab, chosen for their robustness and compatibility with medical

imaging tools and the AI models produced using the nnU-net^[1] architecture.

Ensuring reproducible results

After a model has been trained and validated, a hash for the files containing the trained model weights is calculated. This hash is used to ensure that an image set that is expected to be segmented using a specific model is indeed segmented using that model.

A separate service recomputes the hash for the installed models each night, so any change in the installed models will trigger an error.

Modular Design for Enhanced Functionality

To make the system robust, the four modules have clearly defined and non-overlapping responsibilities. As an image set progresses through the system, only one module handles the data at any given time.

Configurations

The Gateway has a configuration for where it should send files for inference.

Additionally, it has several trigger-configuration files. Each of these has:

- A set of DICOM tags and values that will trigger an inference process.
- Information on where to send the results.
- Information specifying custom changes for the structures needed by the clinicians.
- A "niceness" level. Image sets with lower "niceness" will be processed before image sets with higher values, if multiple image sets are waiting to be processed.
- The hash of the expected model to ensure correct model is used for inference.
- Whether or not to include a structure with metadata on the inference.

To enable the reading and, potentially, changing of these files by technical staff, they are plain-text files with an easy syntax.

We added the "niceness" level to allow for prioritizing inferences, e.g., for online treatments that need the delineations as fast as possible.

The Watchdog module configuration consists of:

- Where it should scan for incoming image sets, and at what interval.
- The command for inference.

The Inference process is configured with:

- System specific nnU-net information
- Structure information, nnU-net arguments for each enabled model

The Return Service mimics the Watchdog service and is configured with:

- Where it should scan for incoming image sets, and at what interval.
- When to clean up image sets that have encountered an error.

Process Management

The Watchdog, Inference and Return service are written in Python 3.11. To ensure robustness, they all implement a main process, which spawns a worker process that does the actual work. The main process monitors and restarts the worker if a crash or any other unrecoverable error happens.

Workflow

In AIS, each image set is processed in a unique, dedicated directory on the inference machine. This directory acts as a central node for all files related to the inference, including configurations, logs, and outputs. The system employs a dynamic directory renaming strategy to reflect the current stage of the inference process, enhancing transparency and trackability. Upon successful completion of the segmentation, the directory and its contents is automatically deleted to maintain system efficiency. In contrast, any failures in the process result in the retention of the directory, along with detailed logs, to facilitate error analysis and resolution.

The naming of the directories follows the format of "STATE_UID" where "STATE" is one of the following: *receiving*, *ready*, *active*, *inferred*, *error* or *handled_error*, and UID is a unique ID for that image set. Each module will only work on a directory in a subset of the possible states, and the renaming happens as the absolute last step of each module.

The representation of state via directory naming was chosen for its simplicity and ease of understanding. This approach ensures that even individuals with limited familiarity with AIS can easily understand and navigate the system's status.

Integration with Clinical Workflow

AIS's design emphasizes minimal disruption to the existing clinical workflow. Automated processes and streamlined data handling ensure that clinicians can access AI-aided segmentations without deviations from standard operational procedures. The system's adaptability allows for easy incorporation of future advancements in AI segmentation algorithms and models.

Communicating metadata to the end-user

AIS employs a simple approach to address the challenge of effectively communicating inference process details to the end-user, especially considering the limitations in DICOM for such metadata transmission. We utilize an empty structure in the generated DICOM-file, which is named to convey information about the AI segmentation process

despite being devoid of segmentation data. This naming convention serves two purposes:

- **Successful Inference:** In cases of successful AI segmentations, the empty struct's name includes the AI model used and the number of DICOM images used for inference. This provides end-users with accessible information about segmentations they are reviewing.
- **Unsuccessful Inference:** If an error occurs during segmentation, the empty structure is named with an error code and a concise description of the issue. This approach allows for rapid identification and understanding of errors, facilitating efficient troubleshooting and resolution without overwhelming the user with technical details.

Including the image count in the metadata is a critical feature, designed to address scenarios where an incomplete image set might be processed due to DICOM transfer failures. By detailing the number of slices in the metadata, AIS empowers users to identify and address such discrepancies quickly, ensuring the integrity of the treatment planning process.

Furthermore, AIS defaults to appending "_AI" to the names of all AI-generated structures. This simple yet effective naming convention allows clinicians to distinguish between manually created and AI-generated structures, thus maintaining clarity in treatment planning and review processes. This feature is configurable and naming can be changed per structure in individual workflows.

Image set filtering

The filtering in the Gateway module allows AIS to accept all image sets, but will only send image sets matching the filters to be inferred. This ensures that a model will only be used to delineate images of the same type as the images it has been trained and validated with. A model trained on CT-images may not be validated on MR-images and should not be used for those. Likewise, a model trained to delineate the male pelvis, should not be used on images of the female pelvis.

3 Results

AIS Deployment

The deployment of the AI Inference Service (AIS) within our radiotherapy department was a smooth process. The primary adjustments post-deployment involved fine-tuning the system's logging capabilities.

Inference Time Efficiency

Depending on the specific image set and model used, the inference process, which starts when an image set has been received and ends when the delineated structures have been delivered, typically takes between 2 and 3.5 minutes, even on consumer-grade GPUs like the NVIDIA 3090. This

duration demonstrates the system's efficiency in handling inference within a reasonable timeframe, fitting well within the clinical workflow.

User Feedback and Workflow Impact

The reception of AIS among clinicians has been positive, even though the system is relatively new in production. While formal data collection and analysis is on-going but not yet finalized, initial user feedback suggests an estimated 30-50% increase in workflow efficiency when using AIS compared to not using AIS.

Challenges in Metadata Communication

A challenge encountered involves the transmission of metadata to end-users. Some treatment planning systems do not support the import of empty structures, hindering the intended communication method. We included a minimal geometric structure within the 'empty' structure to address this. This workaround ensures the conveyance of metadata.

4 Discussion

Extensibility of AIS with External Models

A key aspect of the AIS is its flexibility in integrating AI models. Currently, AIS provides delineation using four models:

- Male Pelvis Model^[2].
- Head and Neck model^[5].
- Heart model^[4].
- Brachytherapy model for cervical cancer.

However, its architecture is designed for easy extension to include externally developed models as well. This adaptability significantly broadens the potential applications of AIS.

Windows-Based System: Constraints and Benefits

Operating AIS on Windows does impose certain constraints, particularly in terms of model compatibility, as nnU-net version 1 models do not run on Windows. Despite this, we believe the benefits, notably the access to comprehensive support from the hospital's larger IT system, outweigh the limitations. This support is crucial for maintaining system stability and reliability, which are paramount in a clinical setting.

DICOM database as a Potential Bottleneck

The integration of part of AIS as an extension in a DICOM database, while beneficial for data handling and processing, has been identified as a bottleneck in terms of total inference time. This may be a hindrance for using AIS in time-critical workflows. Exploring the possibility of excluding the DICOM database from the process could yield improvements in inference speed, enhancing patient experience and treatment efficiency.

Research AIS

A non-clinical variant of AIS, characterized by more flexible or entirely absent filters, is used by researchers and developers to test and validate new models before clinical implementation.

Future Directions

In addition to technical advancements, a significant focus is on optimizing AIS for faster inference times. This is especially critical in real-time treatment scenarios, where prompt decision-making is needed.

5 Conclusion

The implementation of the AIS in our department marks a significant step. AIS has demonstrated its potential to streamline workflows, enhance treatment planning efficiency, and provide high-quality auto-segmentations, proving to be a valuable asset in our radiotherapy treatments.

Key Achievements and Impact:

- AIS's smooth deployment and stable performance highlight its reliability in a clinical setting.
- The system's ability to process image sets efficiently, even with consumer-grade GPUs, illustrates its practicality and scalability.
- Positive feedback from clinicians, suggesting a 50% increase in workflow efficiency, underscores the system's effectiveness and user-friendliness.

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